

Comparative analysis between Welfare Services and wellbeing of retired citizens in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Comparative analysis between Welfare Services and wellbeing of retired citizens in Calabar metropolis of Cross River state Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: determine the relationship between social security (pension scheme); investigate the relationship between affordable low-cost housing; examine the relationship between inexpensive medical services and wellbeing retired citizens. The study adopted mixed method type of research design specifically qualitative and quantitative approach. The population of the study consists of all retired citizens in Calabar metropolis. A sample size of 240 respondents were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. A 4 likert scale questionnaire and 9 itemed Key informant Interview Guide were the instruments of data collection. The data obtained were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation analytical procedure. Findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between social welfare services and wellbeing of retired citizens in Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study concluded that social welfare services impact positively on the wellbeing of retired citizen. Since older people are very vulnerable, government and civil society organizations should help in various ways by providing social welfare services to them.

Keywords: Social welfare services, retired citizens, pension scheme, wellbeing

Introduction

The rapidly growing number of the retired citizen during the last few decades has impacted on the political, economic and social functions of societies. The population division of the United Nations Development of Economic and Social Affairs; population division (UNDESA, 2015) observed that the proportion of older persons aged 60 years and above make up 12.3 percent of the global population and by 2050 that proportion will rise to almost 22 percent. Sub-Saharan Africa, which has the smallest proportion of elderly and which is aging slower than the developed regions, is projected to see the absolute size of its older population grow by 2.3 times between 2000 and 2030 (UNDESA, 2015). People are living longer due to better nutrition, sanitation, healthcare, education and economic wellbeing.

The ageing of populations across the globe is a demographic reality of our time. By 2050, there will be more population of older people worldwide (ages 60 years and over) than children under 15 years (Pelzer, 2012, UNDESA, 2013). Nigeria and other developing countries are now faced with an ageing at a different scale than what is experienced in developed societies. Nigeria is just beginning to experience the ageing transition in full (Pelzer, 2012).

In Nigeria, the aged population too is increasing rapidly. Those aged 65 years and above (the elderly) make up 3.1 percent or 5.9 million of the total population of 200 million, which in crude numbers represent an increase of 600,000 during the 5year period 2012-2017 (National Council on Aging, 2016). The rising number of the elderly in Nigeria may be attributed to the crude mortality rate that is gradually decreasing (Adebowale, & Ayeni, 2012) despite the socio-economic hardship,

widespread poverty, the HIV/AIDS epidemic and the rapid transformation of the traditional extended family structure (Adebanjoke & Ugwoke, 2014). Apart from the decline in fertility, improved health and sanitary conditions have also contributed to the rise in life expectancy (Tanyi, Andre & Mba, 2018). The United Nations in the 1980s projected that by 2025, the number of the aged in Nigeria would have risen from its 27th position in the 1950s to 11th position (United Nations, 1985). Estimates by the United Nations (2012) showed that the elderly population in Nigeria will increase from 6.4 million in 2005 to 11.5 million in 2025, and then 25.5 million by 2050.

Aging causes people to be less active, frail and exposed to more risks of contacting a disease, leading to prejudice or discrimination against the elderly, social isolation and sometimes abandonment. An aging population poses numerous social and economic challenges thus making care of the aged an issue of significant concern. Wellbeing of the aged has become a serious issue because despite the demographic impact of the AIDS epidemic, the Nigerian population is projected to continue ageing over the next two decades. In the midst of this demographic reality, is the fact that Calabar South local government in Cross River State and in Nigeria will be under intense pressure to meet the economic, health, psychological and material well-being challenges of the aged, especially as traditional family support system for the elderly care is breaking down and disappearing (Okoye, 2012). The well-being of the aged is influenced by a number of economic and social factors that include income, mental health, physical health, education, social relationships, employment, discrimination, government policies, and neighborhood conditions. Well-being involves both physical and mental health as part of a holistic approach to health promotion and disease prevention. The well-being of a society has the potential to impact greatly on the people's wellbeing in terms of the productivity level of the society as a whole. Though it may be assessed at the individual level, well-being becomes an important population outcome at the macro level and therefore represents a public health issue.

The refugee crisis, the current and future projections around climate migration, and the changing demographic landscape globally sets forth new questions about our strategies and policies for the aging population, integration of new populations, and the readiness of our communities economically and socially to diversify (Watts, Noye & Tarini, 2022). As demographic shifts and health advancements take hold in Nigeria and globally, how do we create supportive communities for aging now and in the nearest future to guarantee longer life? How does the society support better care during later life? In view of this, social welfare provision becomes necessary as response mechanism for the wellbeing maintenance of the aged. Provisions of social service such as income, securities, housing, health care and even legal assistance can positively influence the wellbeing of the elderly (Oladeyi, 2011). A national social security system will provide an economic buffer in old age. In 1989, the Nigerian government developed the national social development policy which aimed to provide a framework for protecting the elderly persons from morals and materials neglect and provide public assistance when necessary. Despite the development of the national social development policy to care for the elderly, there has been no effective execution of this policy by any federal agency, thus posing a serious challenge to the wellbeing of the elderly (Mbdulkadir, 2016).

It is to note that the rising population of the aged requires social welfare interventions in the form of social security, low cost housing and accessible medical care. Guaranteed social security in form of pension scheme is necessary; it has the potential to reduce poverty and support older people who have disengaged from public service. The aged is entitled to a consistent and inexpensive health care system. Affordable and accessible housing is important in promoting the wellbeing of the aged. If the wellbeing of the elderly members of the community are to be guaranteed, the importance of appropriate housing and social pension (social insurance) cannot be underestimated. Provision of social services such as income, security, health care, housing, and legal assistance can positively influence the well-being and health of the elderly (Oladeji, 2011).

The aged family members lack access to economic resources, basic services, markets; affected by poverty, hunger and inequality (Pelzer, 2012). Apart from disadvantages experienced in purely economic dimension, they are unable to meet basic needs, also, inability to participate in economic, social, civil and political life (Pelzer, 2012). The interest in family sustainability has been raised due to its declining nutritional levels which is seriously affecting the aged members who are experiencing poor health care accessibility, non-involvement in community political affairs and increasing poverty level (Pelzer, 2012).

The wellbeing of the aged poses a serious concern to social workers, concerned citizens and the entire society. The older persons and their families face challenges in coping with functional wellbeing due to changes in family dynamics, increased demand for medical services, increased economic stress and decreased functional independence. Ani (2013) observed that health status of the aged is a function of the care and support they receive. Several chronic diseases suffered by the aged are traceable to lack of or inadequate care and support as well as poor nutrition and physical inactivity. In Nigeria, evidence shows a very weak institutional base to tackle the care and support of the elderly (Okoye, 2011).

Since poverty remains a major challenge in Nigeria, elderly persons who have retired from the economic productive phase are most vulnerable to experiencing economic hardship (Oladeji, 2011). Since the statutory age of retirement in Nigeria is 60 and 70 years (depending on where you work) and is the cut-off for being categorized as an elderly person, the majority of

this group of (elderly) people are not socially and economically secure (Oladeji, 2011). Elderly people are usually forced to cope with the paradox of dwindling financial resources. In particular, elderly people living in urban areas in Nigeria only utilized health services and other services when they are available, accessible, and affordable (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014).

The patterns of the economic lives of older persons in Nigeria vary by urban and rural residences (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014). In urban Nigeria, elders with high physical and psychological functioning are forced to retire once they reach the statutory retirement age. They face abrupt declines in their income and can feel less self-worth or even experience depression, since they perceive themselves as still being fit to work. Gureje & Oyewole (2006) were of the view that implicit social changes reduce the status of the elderly and their influence in the society which affect their total wellbeing. The majority of them are faced with depression, loss of vision, diabetes, hypertension, obesity, tooth loss, pathological bone fracture, arthritis and rheumatism, stroke, Alzheimer's disease, etc. (Ani, 2019).

Some of the challenges associated with the elderly in both urban and rural areas are the diseases that come with old age and the lack of well-trained doctors to care for them especially in rural areas (Ayomele, 2017). In some urban areas there are no trained geriatric doctors incorporated into the health-care system to take care of the health needs of the elderly. The non-establishment of geriatric hospitals or availability of geriatric sections incorporated in teaching hospitals to care for the elderly is part of the problems encountered by the elderly (Ayomele, 2017).

The lack of framework for supportive and protective care that comprises those services provided to frail, ill, or disabled older people to support them and their caretakers while maintaining their capacity to live in the community exacerbates the adverse condition of the elderly (Ayomele, 2017). In rural Nigeria, many older persons are not formally employed with a company or civil service, they continue to engage in menial jobs and manual work on the farms with meager earnings as long as their physical strength can afford (Ayomele, 2017). The rural elderly may suffer from health disorders and physical exhaustion and often have no retirement benefits to serve as social security.

Thus, an ageing population has implications for labour markets, health care and social security. Wellbeing of the aged in Calabar South local government area of Cross River State poses a serious challenge because of relatively low level of socio-economic development. Calabar South local government Council is unable to respond to the plight of large numbers of elderly people, especially as traditional family support systems for the elderly are breaking down due to globalization (Adebanjoko & Ugwuoke, 2014). So far, there has been no clearly defined policy intervention on this issue thus the interest in the wellbeing of the aged has become a pressing very challenging in this local government area.

The lack of deliberate intervention in the form of social welfare services for the aged may be exacerbating their marginalized condition. The elderly needs policy intervention for care and protection such as social welfare. Social welfare services will help to meet the economic, health, psychological and material wellbeing challenges of the elderly. Therefore, the provision of social security, low cost housing and free medical care could bridge the gap in the wellbeing of retired aged citizens in Calabar South local government area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the relationship between social security (pension scheme) and wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area municipal of Cross River State
2. To Investigate the relationship between affordable low- cost housing and wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South Local government area municipal of Cross River State
3. To examine the relationship between inexpensive medical services and wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South Local government area municipal of Cross River State

Hypotheses

1. Social security (pension scheme) has no significant relationship with the wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area. municipal of Cross River State
2. Affordable low- cost housing has no significant relationship with the wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area. municipal of Cross River State
3. Availability of free/inexpensive medical services have no significant relationship with wellbeing of the aged retired citizens in Calabar South local government area. municipal of Cross River State

Literature review

Social welfare provision and wellbeing of the aged

People are living longer because of better nutrition, sanitation, health care, education, and economic well-being. An ageing population poses numerous social and economic challenges, but the right set of policies can equip society to address

these challenges in time. Nigeria's elderly too is increasing rapidly. In Nigeria, those aged 65 years and above (the elderly) make up 3.1% or 5.9 million of the total population of 191 million, which in crude numbers represents an increase of 600,000 during the 5-year period 2012–2017 (Population Reference Bureau, 2012; National Council on Ageing 2016).

Ageing in Nigeria is occurring against the background of socioeconomic hardship, widespread poverty, the HIV/AIDS epidemic, and the rapid transformation of the traditional extended family structure (Adebanjoko & Ugwuoke, 2014). This makes the intersection between social welfare services provision and wellbeing by the elderly very paramount (Nkpoyen, 2011). The UNDP indicators of wellbeing include people's ability to live long, healthy and creative lives in an equitable society and in a sustainable way as well as their level of income; employment opportunities open to them, access to basic services such as education and training basic infrastructure etc (Decancq & Lugo 2013). The index of social exclusion assessing the extent of inclusion covers three dimensions, economic exclusion, exclusion from social services and exclusion from civic participation (Medgyesi, Ozdenir & Ward, 2017).

The economic dimension covers deprivation in respect of income and basic needs, access to employment, financial services and material assets, the lack of amenities that the household needs but cannot afford and housing space. The social services dimension contains indicators on access to, and the affordability of, education and healthcare services as well as public utilities. The civic and social life dimension includes indicators of access to political, cultural and social participation and support networks, as well as the frequency of social and civic participation (Medgyesi, Ozdenir and Ward, 2017).

Social security (pension scheme) and wellbeing of the aged

The growth in the number of older people inevitably has brought an increase in the range and intensity of their problems and needs. For those who are in the public sector, the pension scheme appears to be the source of social securities (Tanimon, 2006, Oshiomole, 2009). The pension reform Act 2004 provides, among others, that, the scheme shall apply to all employees in the public service of the Nigerian federation, federal capital territory and the private sector organization in which these are five or more employees. According to Oshiomoke (2009), the objectives of the schemes were to ensure that every person who worked in either the public service of the federation, federal capital territory or private sector received his retirement benefit as and when due.; assist improvident individuals by ensuring that they save in other to cater for their livelihood during old age etc. Thus, the pension scheme has the potential to ameliorate their suffering and care for them. (Ogumbameru & Adesina, 2000).

Affordable low-cost housing and wellbeing for the aged

The home environment that does not meet physical needs is not likely to be satisfactory to the aged. Thus, provision of the low-cost housing accommodation is desirable. This aging of the population presents a number of challenges and unanswered questions including where people will live, whether they will afford it and how they will obtain support and care they will need as they age while retaining as much independence as possible. (Green & Painter, 2012). Affordable housing options with low-income housing tax credit or public housing-linked with health and supportive services may provide a cost-effective answer for meeting the needs of lower-income services may provide a cost-effective answer for meeting the needs of lower-income services (Sanders, 2019).

Access to medical services and care of the aged

The provision of quality assured health care services for the elderly population is a challenge that requires government continuous response, failure to address the health needs today could develop into a costly problem tomorrow. Akanyi and Baryewa (2002) commented that the need for improved attention to the health needs of the older people through improved budgeting allocation, revision of the training curriculum of all cadres of health staff to include geriatrics and utilization of primary health care facilities cannot be over-emphasized. At the first national summit on healthy ageing in Abuja, the federal government said it plans to extend free health care services to all Nigerians over the age of 60 years. (Daily trust, 2019).

The basic needs approach and political economy perspective of aging

The basic needs approach and political economy perspective of aging constituted the theoretical framework and was introduced by International Labour Organization's World Employment Conference in 1976 (Jolly 1976). The satisfaction of basic human needs is the overriding objectives of social welfare policy. This is necessary for the survival of the elderly. The political economy perspective implies that in the context of capitalist society, the elderly people who are in a weak position in the global economy requires access to social welfare especially medical services and low-cost housing.

Methodology

The research adopted for this study was the qualitative and quantitative approaches of survey design. The population of the study comprised all the aged Citizens inhabitants from the age of 55 to 70 years retired Citizens in these wards made up

the study population in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The rationale for targeting only retirees was because they were educated and exposed to policy issues in Nigeria. Calabar South Local Government has 12 political wards that constituted the 12 strata. Twenty (20) respondents were selected from each stratum. The actual selection was done through systematic and snowball sampling procedures. Only 240 literate elderly men and women from the clusters were studied. Therefore, the sample of the study was made up of 240 respondents. The sample comprised retirees from the public service residing in the communities Calabar South Local Government Area Cross River State. A pretesting was done to ascertain the reliability and validity of the questionnaire and Key Informant Guide. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyzed data based on each of the hypotheses.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Social security (Pension Scheme) has no significant relationship with wellbeing of the aged retired citizen in Calabar South local government area

Table 1: Pearson product moment correlation coefficient analysis of the relationship between social security (Pension Scheme) and wellbeing of the aged (n = 200)

Variable	X	SD	$\sum X$	$\frac{\sum X^2}{\sum Y}$	$\frac{\sum XY}{\sum Y^2}$	r-cal
Social security		11.19	1.77	3780	70560	0.415
Wellbeing of aged (Y)	12.20	2.21	6820	12980	67840	

*Correlation significant $p > .05$, $df = 198$, $crit - r = 0.196$

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Hypotheses 2:

Affordable low- cost housing has no significant relationship with the wellbeing of aged retired citizens in Calabar South Local Government

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient analysis of the relationship between affordable low-cost housing and wellbeing of the aged (n = 200)

Variable	X	SD	$\sum X$	$\frac{\sum X^2}{\sum Y^2}$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
Affordable low-cost housing (X)	12.11	1.47	5780	70560	97540	8.212*
Wellbeing of aged (Y)	17.11	2.27	6820	12980		

*Correlation significant $p > .05$, $df = 198$, $crit - r = 0.196$

Source: Field survey, 2024

Hypothesis 3:

Accessibility to medical service has no significant relationship with wellbeing of the aged in Calabar South local government Area

Table 3: Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient analysis of the relationship between inexpensive medical service and wellbeing of aged retired citizen (n = 200)

Variable	X	SD	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
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		ΣY	ΣY^2			
Inexpensive medical service X	12.76	1.44	4770	139800		
Wellbeing of aged (Y)	14.11	3.31	6820	12980	11910	0.321*

*Correlation significant $p > .05$, $df = 198$, $\text{crit } r = 0.196$

Source: Field survey, 2024

Discussion of Findings

The result of statistical analyses revealed that social security (pension scheme), access to medical services and housing all have significant relationships with the wellbeing of the aged. From the analysis, the value was positive which indicated that the more the availability of social security the better the wellbeing of the aged. According to Apere (2015), the problems that surround pensioners in Nigeria include: (1) Delayed or nonpayment of pension entitlements and misappropriation of existing pension funds; (2) low standard of living (or high poverty incidence) among pensioners due to pension increases not in line with salary inflation or no pension increase at all; (3) too frequent verification of pensioners by pension transitional arrangements directorate (PTAD) (section 42 of PRA 2014) leading to pensioners dying during verification exercises; (4) inadequate enforcement of pension regulation: After more than 10 years of existence of the CPS, not all state governments had enacted their pension laws to establish the CPS, which is a sign of regulatory weakness (Apere, 2015).

Nkpoyen (2015) observed that social policy issues including pension are very significant for ensuring social protection for the aged in poor countries. In Nigeria about seventy percent of the citizens are living below the poverty line of one dollar a day public sector. Real wages are not only low but dismally downward. Old age security is not available outside formal occupation and unemployment benefit are not provided for the unemployed, meaning that the workers under the extended family system take responsibility for this vulnerable group (Smalley, 2010). This study agrees with Ogumbameou and Adesina (2020) that the pension scheme has the potential to ameliorate the suffering of the aged and care for them.

A Key informant respondent, former Chairperson aged 61 years reported that: The greatest problem we have in this country is that our leaders don't keep to their words. The people managing the pension scheme don't keep their word. Many elderly people like us who depend on pension suffer to get their pension, many even die before the pension starts coming. Some of the elderly who are retired cannot even pay their rents. Some who retire and move to the rural areas die immediately they get home because of suffering (KII 2023).

Oladeji (2020) commented that since poverty remains a major challenge in Nigeria, elderly persons who have retired from the economic productive phase are most vulnerable to experiencing economic hardship. Since the statutory age of retirement in Nigeria is 60 and 70 years (depending on where you work) and is the cut-off for being categorized as an elderly person, the majority of this group of (elderly) people are not socially and economically secure. Elderly people are usually forced to cope with the paradox of dwindling financial resources, increased health challenges, and a geometric rise in medical expenses. In particular, elderly people living in urban areas in Nigeria only utilized health services and other services when they were available, accessible, and affordable (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014).

The patterns of the economic lives of older persons in Nigeria vary by urban and rural residences (Odaman & Ibiezugbe, 2014). In urban Nigeria, elders with high physical and psychological functioning are forced to retire once they reach the statutory retirement age. They face abrupt declines in their income and can feel less self-worth or even experience depression, since they perceive themselves as still being fit to work.

One Key Informant respondents, aged 54 years articulated the situation as follows: in our communities, we older persons are not formally employed with a company or some other form of governmental organization, we continue to engage in menial jobs and manual work on the farms with meager earnings as long as their physical strength can afford. We have no access to free medical services when we are sick. We suffer from health disorders and physical exhaustion and often have no access to retirement benefits to serve as social security.

The findings are consistent with Warding (2015) that the overwhelming majority and older adult prefer to age in their place, remaining in their current home or communities. However, many senior citizens feel that their current homes are not well suited for aging. A home environment that does not meet physical needs is not likely to be satisfactory to the aged. Thus, provision of the low-cost housing accommodation is desirable to the aged. Community features, house affordability and accessibility of services all contribute to the ability of the senior citizens to successfully age in their current home and labour.

The findings validate Kojetin (2017) that safe and accessible housing and services are essential to maintain maximum health, functioning and independence in the older population. According to Kojetin (2015) a handful of empirical studies indicate evidence of improved health outcomes, enhanced productive engagement and public cost-saving attributable to various interventions such as housing accommodation that encourage aging in place.

As observed by Sanders (2019) and supported by the findings of this study, the provision of low -cost housing to serve the needs of the elderly has the potential advantages such as building on an existing infrastructure of housing and community service networks; also helping preserve seniors' autonomy and independence. The result of statistical analysis revealed that inexpensive medical services significantly relate to the care of the aged. Therefore, as commended by Akanji and Banyewa (2018) which is validated by the study, the need for improved attention to the health needs of the older people through improved budgetary allocation, revision of the training curriculum of all cadres of health staff to include geriatrics and utilization of primary health care facilities cannot be over emphasized.

The findings are in tandem with Shrivastara, Shrivastara and Ramasaney (2013) observed that the health needs or health related problems of the elderly people cannot be viewed in isolation. Provision of care for the elderly is very essential. One of the Key Informants respondents, aged 57 years asserted that: Most of the elderly people residing in the rural communities have no support from the government. They get support from faith-based organizations or from their relatives and some none at all. Elderly people who don't have any relatives suffer a lot in this local government area.

Another Key Informant, aged 50 years commented that: the elderly ones in our communities are suffering. In this community there are no basic amenities. For example, people have to walk so many kilometers to get drinking water, electricity is not regular. The elderly in the rural communities cannot even afford electricity bills, there are no health facilities in this community. The elderly have to travel long distances to get medical attention. The rate of suffering is just too much. The government has not done anything to improve the lives of the elderly in this community.

Conclusion

Specifically, the provision of social security (pension scheme), affordable low-cost housing and inexpensive medical service are required to sustain the aged members of the society. The institutional care of the aged is vital to enable them access social security services.

Recommendations

1. Regular payment of statutory pension should be punished by the government.
2. The growth in the number of older people inevitably has brought an increase in the range and intensity of their problems especially that of housing. So, the government should make the provision of affordable housing a priority policy.
3. Older people are very vulnerable to diseases; therefore, the government should ensure that medical services are available and affordable.

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